

ADMAIORA

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Project title: ADvanced nanocomposite MAterIals fOr in situ treatment and
ultrASound-mediated management of osteoarthritis

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D 7.8

Report on 2nd ADMAIORA workshop and other key communication events

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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Service)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Service)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Service)	

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1 Executive summary

This Deliverable describes the key events organised in the second year of the ADMAIORA project, as devised in the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. In particular, the second project-related **scientific symposium** was proposed and accepted for the 47th European Society of Artificial Organs (ESAO) Congress by the Project Coordinator. Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 pandemic, the 47th ESAO Congress was postponed to 2021. Furthermore, a **technical webinar** was organised within the event **Tech Share Day 2020**, with a focus on regenerative medicine and artificial organs.

A second **non-technical Workshop** has also been organised (it will take place in February 2021) by the Project Coordinator in collaboration with IOR, addressing clinical end-users, namely orthopedists, radiologists and other people interested in imaging and diagnostics. Here the speakers will discuss recent developments and potential future applications of diagnostic and therapeutic ultrasound for osteoarticular applications and beyond, highlighting the challenges yet to be addressed and the possible future impact of this technology, highlighting the links with the ADMAIORA project efforts.

Finally, this Deliverable describes the following **additional communication events**:

- Two articles describing the ADMAIORA project on a quarterly magazine (*Il Notiziario del Malato Reumatico*), edited by an association of patients supporting the ADMAIORA project (*Associazione Malati Reumatici Emilia Romagna*, AMRER);
- A TV interview delivered by Prof. Ricotti to the RAI – Italian State Broadcaster, on ADMAIORA and the new frontiers of regenerative medicine;
- Press release for a scientific paper published in the journal *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*;
- Promotional video “ADMAIORA turns 1 year”, promoted on the social networks.

2 Introduction

The dissemination plan, described in Deliverable D7.2 - Preliminary report of the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, includes presentations at scientific and technological events. In particular, one Workshop per year dedicated to the ADMAIORA themes is foreseen to present the project results to a broad audience of potential users, stakeholders, and scientists. To this purpose, the Project Coordinator proposed a **symposium** focused on a scientific topic closely adherent to the ADMAIORA scope during the **47th European Society of Artificial Organs (ESAO) Congress** and the submitted proposal was accepted. The title of the event was "*Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration*" (see section 3.1) Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 pandemic, 47th ESAO Congress was postponed to 2021.

Furthermore, the Coordinator was invited as a speaker the **Tech Share Day 2020**, the digital event related to the trending topics of biotechnology and biomedical sciences, in the event "Artificial, bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs". His presentation was entitled "Artificial, bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs" (see section 2.2).

According to Deliverable D7.2, within special communication activities, four non-technical Workshops are expected to be organised during all the project duration to communicate results to healthcare system actors and stakeholders. These events also serve to share with osteoarthritis (OA) patients and in general elderly people, the technologies that are under development in the project, thus to prevent possible barriers to a future adoption of the project results. In particular, two events are expected for healthcare system actors and stakeholders and two for OA patients and elderly people. In this context, a technical Workshop on ultrasounds and their applications (see section 3.3) has been organised and will be held on February 19th by SSSA in collaboration with IOR, addressing clinical end-users, such as orthopedists, radiologists, and other professionals interested in ultrasound-based imaging and diagnostics. During this workshop, entitled "*Ultrasuoni: l'innovazione dalla diagnostica alla terapia*", recent developments and potential future applications of diagnostic and therapeutic ultrasound for osteoarticular applications and beyond will be discussed.

Finally, this Deliverable describes the following communication events:

- Two articles describing the ADMAIORA project have been printed on "*Notiziario del Malato Reumatico*", a quarterly magazine edit by AMRER (section 4.1)
- A TV interview delivered by Prof. Ricotti (RAI – Italian State Broadcaster) on the ADMAIORA approach and the new frontiers of regenerative medicine (section 4.2)
- A press release was organised for a scientific paper published in the journal ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces (section 4.3)
- A promotional video "ADMAIORA turns 1 year" was produced and shared through the project social networks (section 4.4)

3 Technical and non-technical Workshops within ADMAIORA

3.1 Symposium on "*Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration*", 47th ESAO Congress

A Symposium proposal was submitted at the 47th ESAO Congress, originally planned to be held on September 8-12, 2020 in London (UK).

This Symposium was organised by Prof. Leonardo Ricotti as Chair, in collaboration with Prof. Sonia Fiorilli, Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy, as Co-Chair. This event was also designed to

create synergies between two H2020 projects on the theme of regenerative medicine and funded in the same Call, namely ADMAIORA (<https://www.admaiora-project.com/>) and GIOTTO (<https://www.giottoproject.eu/>). Furthermore, a link to another H2020-funded project, namely MagTendon - ERC-CoG (<https://achilles.i3bs.eu/>) was targeted.

The Symposium was entitled "*Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration*" and it touched themes related to osteoarticular tissues regeneration, stem cells, innovative biomaterials and smart devices.

The abstract of the Symposium is reported below:

"This Symposium tackles the theme of osteoarticular tissues regeneration, by presenting the most research efforts in this field, led by important European actors.

Stem cells, innovative biomaterials and smart devices enabling advanced functionalities and new therapeutic strategies will constitute the focus of this event, with the aim to solve unmet clinical challenges related to bone-related diseases (e.g., osteoporosis) and cartilage-related pathologies (e.g., osteoarthritis) and tendon/ligament degeneration or traumas.

The keynote talk will analyse the variegated and interdisciplinary research domain of biomaterials for osteoarticular tissues regeneration. Then, the subsequent talks will provide an overview of cutting-edge research carried out in different ambitious projects funded by the European Community, which propose potentially ground-breaking solutions for cartilage, bone and tendon regeneration, bringing such innovation as close as possible to a future clinical translation."

The overall duration of the Symposium was set to 90 minutes. One keynote speaker and four speakers were invited to give their presentation on themes related to the Symposium.

The list of speakers is reported below:

Keynote Speaker

Prof. **Luigi Ambrosio** (Institute of Polymers, Composites & Biomaterials, National Research Council, Naples, Italy)

Talk title: "Biomaterials for osteoarticular tissues regeneration: from basic research to the clinics"

Speakers

1. Prof. **Leonardo Ricotti** (The BioRobotics Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy)
Talk title: "Smart materials and ultrasound for cartilage healing: the ADMAIORA project"
(<https://www.admaiora-project.com/>)

2. Prof. **Sonia Fiorilli** (Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy)
Talk title: "Smart nanobiomaterials and 3D fabrication technologies to face osteoporosis: the challenge of the GIOTTO project"
(<https://www.giottoproject.eu/>)

3. **Manuela Gomes** (3Bs Research Group, University of Minho, Portugal)
Talk title: "Stem cells and gene therapy for tendon regeneration"
(<https://achilles.i3bs.eu/>) (MagTendon, ERC - CoG)

4. **Joshua Kaggie** (Department of Radiology, University of Cambridge, UK)
Talk title: "Advanced imaging and stem cell tracking: a transversal enabling technology"
(<http://starstem.eu/project/project-posters/>)

Due to COVID-19 pandemic, the 47th ESAO Congress was postponed to 2021 as explained in the announcement on the Congress website (Figure 1 and Figure 2). The Symposium, with the same structure, will be thus held in September 2021.

ESAO Events

 47th ESAO Congress www.esao2020.org

European Society for Artificial Organs

8-12 September 2020
Brunel University London, Uxbridge, UK

Uniting scientific minds towards lasting artificial organs

47th ESAO Congress

Difficult Times and Difficult Decision: ESAO 2020 in London is postponed to 2021

Information about Postponement

London, Uxbridge, UK
www.esao2020.org
Abstract submission

Figure 1: Announcement of postponement of the 47th ESAO Congress on the website (<https://www.esao.org/>).

Dear Friends and Colleagues,

Strange Times - Difficult Decisions

After much consideration we have made the difficult but required decision in conjunction with the ESAO Executive Committee, to postpone ESAO 2020 to 2021 at Brunel University London.

Obviously, this is very disappointing, as we know how much ESAO annual conference means to everyone. We assure you this decision was not taken lightly or in haste, but we are still some distance from the peak of this dangerous pandemic and no date at sight to when might normal working conditions are restored. With lockdown in most countries, restrictions on movements and travel bans, we had no real choice, but to postpone.

We thank you and the whole ESAO membership for understanding the extreme difficulty of this decision and for your commitment to the success of ESAO yearly conference. Specifically, we profoundly appreciate all of the abstracts submitted, which we plan to publish in the International Journal of Artificial Organs, as originally planned (more information to the corresponding authors will be sent out next week).

In a spirit of optimism please mark September 2021 in your diaries. Meanwhile, take very good care of yourselves.

Yours sincerely with all good wishes,

Prof. Ashraf W Khir, Congress President, on behalf of the organising Committee.

Prof. Piotr Ladyzynski, ESAO President, on behalf of ESAO Executive Committee.

Figure 2: Information about the postponement of the 47th ESAO Congress by the organising Committee and the ESAO Executive Committee explaining the decision to postpone the 2020 Congress to 2021, due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.2 Technical webinar on “Artificial, bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs”, TechShare

Tech Share Day 2020 ran from the 11th to the 13th of November 2020, with the aim of highlighting the research and innovations pioneered by Italian Universities in trending topics of Biotechnology and Biomedical Sciences. More than 500 Biotech and Biomed innovations were showcased at the event seeking for collaboration opportunities. The event was open to investors and scouters across the globe who took part in the webinars and shared their views during the discussions. The list of all events is reported at the following link:

<https://www.knowledge-share.eu/en/event/tech-share-day-2020/>

On November 11th, the session on ‘Artificial, Bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs’ had Leonardo Ricotti, Alberto Mazzoni, Martina Maselli and Gioia Lucarini as speakers. They described solutions to help patients suffering from diabetes, osteoarthritis, neurological disorders, urinary incontinence and heart disease, also focusing on the challenges and opportunities that Industry and Academia collaborations hold.

The presentation of Prof. Ricotti was entitled: “Artificial, bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs”. A few slides regarding the ADMAIORA project of the presentation are shown in Figure 3.

Artificial, bioartificial and tissue-engineered organs

Leonardo Ricotti

Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy

November 11, 2020

- Artificial pancreas
- Material and system for the treatment of joints
- Device for cardiac electrical stimulation

ADMAIORA (ADvanced nanocomposite MAterials fOr in situ treatment and ulTRAsound-mediated management of osteoarthritis)

Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Organisation type	Country
Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (Coordinator)	SSSA	University	Italy
Bar Ilan University	BIU	University	Israel
Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli	IOR	Hospital	Italy
Image Guided Therapy SA	IGT	SME	France
PlasmaChem GmbH	PLASMACHEM	SME	Germany
Vimex Sp. z o. o.	VIMEX	SME	Poland
H&D Wireless AB	HDW	SME	Sweden

Project start: January 1, 2019
 Duration: 49 months
 Overall budget: 5.4 M€

Call: H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2018-2020
 Grant number no. 815513

ADMAIORA

Target pathology: Osteoarthritis (OA)

Healthy knee

Mild OA

Kellgren and Lawrence (KL) radiographic score

0	I	II	III	IV
Normal	Doubtful	Mild	Moderate	Severe

↓

ADMAIORA clinical target

"Minimally invasive regenerative therapies may possibly lead toward a more successful control and even cure of OA in its infancy"

Moderate OA

Severe OA

Results on nanocomposite materials

Therapeutic patches

Scienze

HOME POLITICA ECONOMIA SPORTI SPETTACOLI TECNOLOGIA MOTORI TUTTE LE SEZIONI D. REF TV

Un microcerotto per rigenerare le cartilagini

Vannozzi, L., Gouveia, P., Pinguet, P., Canale, C., & Ricotti, L. (2020). Novel Ultrathin Films Based on a Blend of PEG-b-PCL and PLLA and Doped with ZnO Nanoparticles. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*. 12(19): 21398

Results on nanocomposite materials

Diffusivity tests

Injectable hydrogels

VG-3D 1:1

VG-3D 1:2

Cell viability

Cell type: human adipose stem cells (ASCs)
 Cell density: 2×10^6 cells/mL
 Live/Dead merged images

1:1

1:2

VG

VG-RGD

Results on engineered ultrasound stimulation

ADMAIORA final objective

ADMAIORA aims to: **slow down joint degeneration in OA animal models**

- 60% reduction of degeneration in OA animal models treated with the ADMAIORA technologies with respect to control (untreated) ones, after 4 weeks
- 90% reduction after 3 months

The session was followed by approximately 90 participants.

The event was adequately promoted on:

- the LinkedIn page of the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (see Figure 4) at the following link: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/scuola-superiore-sant%27anna_techshareday2020-tsd2020-tto-activity-6736611098398638080-rh_b/.
The total number of interactions with the related post on the social networks page was 72.
- The Facebook account of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna and the Biorobotics Institute (Figure 5), available at the following links: <https://www.facebook.com/165421993522527/posts/3617302318334460/?sfnsn=scwspm0>
https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=3656774504387241&id=165421993522527&scmts=scwspstd
The total number of interactions with the related posts on the social networks pages was 48 and 20, respectively.
- The Twitter account of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna at the following link: <https://twitter.com/ScuolaSantAnna/status/1325826302180519941?s=20>
The total number of interactions with the related post on the social network page was 10.
- The YouTube link with the video of the webinar is available at the following link: <https://youtu.be/93WEbbabTns>

Figure 4: Post on the LinkedIn page of the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, advertising the event.

Figure 5: Post on the Facebook page of the Biorobotics Institute, advertising the event.

3.3 Workshop on Therapeutic Ultrasound

This Workshop has been organised by Prof. Leonardo Ricotti (SSSA), Dr. Alessandro Russo (IOR) and Dr. Paolo Spinnato (IOR) and will be held on February 19th, 2021, in order to have time for broad dissemination of the event. The objective of the Workshop is to explore therapeutic ultrasound, an increasingly used tool in the medical field, which is being successfully explored in the ADMAIORA project.

The Workshop is entitled: "*Ultrasuoni: l'innovazione dalla diagnostica alla terapia*" (English translation "Ultrasound: innovation from diagnosis to therapy"). It addresses mainly orthopaedists, radiologists and other clinicians interested in imaging and diagnostics.

A request to the Italian Ministry of Health has been filed to obtain CME Credits for the Workshop (Italian Provider: Biomedica), thus to increase the participation by clinicians, to give more visibility to ADMAIORA project and to provide this Workshop also with an educational role.

The target categories will be: Health assistants, biologists, chemists, physicists, physiotherapists, surgeons, orthopaedic technicians, health technicians of medical radiology. The educational objectives will focus on: a) diagnostic and therapeutic innovation of ultrasound in clinic and research; b) evaluation and improvement of biomedical technologies; c) health technology assessment.

The registration to the Workshop will be free of charge at the following link: <https://bvent.biomedica.net/s/3105>

The participants, in order to be eligible for ECM credits, should:

- attend 90% of the training hours
- pass the learning test (75% of correct answers).

Once passed the test, the participants will be able to print the ECM certificate directly from the site. The ECM questionnaire will be available on the online platform from February 20th to 22nd, 2021. The Workshop will allow getting 3 ECM Credits.

Draft of the agenda (translated in English):

- 16.00-16.10 Leonardo Ricotti, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa**
Introduction to the Workshop
- 16.10-16.25 Marco Miceli, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna**
Historical notes on ultrasound diagnostics
- 16.25-16.40 Alessandro Russo, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna**
Application of ultrasound in arthritic pathology: from scientific evidence to therapeutic innovation
- 16.40-16.55 Paolo Spinnato, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna**
Role of ultrasound in musculoskeletal degenerative and oncological pathologies
- 16.55-17.10 Angela Sorriento, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa**
Quantitative ultrasound imaging for assessing the degree of bone and cartilage tissue degeneration
- 17.10-17.25 Andrea Cafarelli, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa**
Controlled therapeutic ultrasound for regenerative medicine - the ADMAIORA treatment
- 17.25-17.40 Francesco Prada, Istituto Neurologico Carlo Besta, Milano**
Ultrasound for imaging and therapy in neurosurgery
- 17.40-18.01 Questions & Answers and Conclusions (20 min)**

We are preparing a flyer (Figure 6) to disseminate the event through the social networks, the ADMAIORA Website and dedicated newsletters to reach clinicians.

The outcomes of the Workshop will be described in the next months, in D7.10.

**ULTRASUONI:
L'INNOVAZIONE
DALLA
DIAGNOSTICA
ALLA
TERAPIA**

CATEGORIE ACCREDITATE:
Assistente Sanitario,
Biologo, Chimico, Fisico,
Fisioterapista, Medico
Chirurgo, Tecnico
Ortopedico, Tecnico
Sanitario di
Radiologia Medica

OBIETTIVI FORMATIVI E AREA FORMATIVA:
- Innovazione diagnostica e terapeutica degli ultrasuoni in clinica e ricerca
- Valutazione, miglioramento delle tecnologie biomediche
- Health Technology Assessment

Agenda

16.00 - 16.10 Introduzione al workshop
Leonardo Ricotti, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa

16.10 - 16.25 Cenni storici sulla diagnostica ecografica
Marco Miceli, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna

16.25 - 16.40 Applicazione degli ultrasuoni nella patologia artrosica: dall'evidenza scientifica all'innovazione terapeutica
Alessandro Russo, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna

16.40 - 16.55 Ruolo degli ultrasuoni nella patologia degenerativa e oncologica muscolo-scheletrica
Paolo Spinnato, Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, Bologna

16.55 - 17.10 Imaging ad ultrasuoni quantitativo per la valutazione del grado di degenerazione del tessuto osseo e cartilagineo
Angela Sorriento, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa

17.10 - 17.25 Ultrasuoni terapeutici controllati per medicina rigenerativa - il trattamento ADMAIORA
Andrea Cafarelli, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa

17.25 - 17.40 Ultrasuoni per imaging e terapia in neurochirurgia
Francesco Prada, Istituto Neurologico Carlo Besta, Milano

17.40 - 18.00 Domande e conclusioni

Questo lavoro ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal programma di ricerca e innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione europea, Grant Agreement n. 814413, progetto ADMAIORA (Advanced nanocomposite MATERIALs for in situ treatment and ultrASound-mediated management of osteoarthritis).

Figure 6: Flyer of the Workshop on therapeutic ultrasound.

4 Other key communication events

4.1 Articles on the "Notiziario del Malato Reumatico"

Two articles regarding ADMAIORA projects have been published on the "Notiziario del Malato Reumatico" a quarterly magazine registered in court in Bologna n. 7762 of 5/06/2007, published by AMRER, an Italian association of rheumatic patients. On the cover page of the magazine, one of the ADMAIORA articles is the cover story as visible in Figure 7 (left).

The two articles have a different journalistic slant:

- the first one describes the project in a synthetic and general way (Figure 7, right);
- the second one addresses more in detail the technical and scientific aspects of the project (Figure 8).

The magazine has been printed in 5000 pieces and AMRER has sent hard copies to 3400 AMRER associates (end-users). Furthermore, AMRER has distributed free of charge approximately 500 hard copies to on-site conferences and to 24 rheumatology hub centres and clinics in Emilia Romagna.

Finally, a copy of the magazine has been sent by email to about 8000 addresses, including 500 Italian rheumatologists.

The magazine is also available on the AMRER website at the following link:

http://www.amrer.it/download_documenti/AMRER-Notiziario47.pdf

Figure 7: (left): cover page of "Il notiziario del malato reumatico", mentioning ADMAIORA; (right): first article on the ADMAIORA Project.

4.2 TV interview to RAI – Italian State Broadcaster

On September 29th, 2020, the Project Coordinator was interviewed at “Fuori TG”, a Rai tv program, on the new frontiers of regenerative medicine. The main topic of the interview was the ADMAIORA vision, namely a new treatment to fight osteoarthritis with enormous benefits on direct and indirect costs for the European healthcare systems.

The full interview (in Italian) is available on:

- 1- Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna website and social channels at the following link:

<https://www.santannapisa.it/it/multimedia/rai-3-progetto-admaiora-losteoartrite-obiettivo-rivoluzionarne-il-trattamento-meno-costi>

<https://www.facebook.com/165421993522527/videos/685177755437763>

- 2- ADMAIORA Website and Facebook Channels:

<https://www.admaiora-project.com/news/press-review-rai-italian-state-broadcaster-interviews-leonardo-ricotti/>

<https://www.facebook.com/AdmaioraResearchProject/videos/692156808090059>

The typical audience of the TV program “Fuori TG” is approximately **1 million people**.

4.3 Press release for a paper published in ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces

A press release was organised (Figure 9) in correspondence to the publication of a scientific paper¹ in the journal “ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces” (May 4th, 2020). The study, coordinated by The BioRobotics Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, was supported by the EU-funded H2020 ADMAIORA research project.

Figure 9: Internet press release on the Scuola Sant’Anna website.

The press release had significant resonance in Italy and has been disseminated through many channels:

- 1- Ansa, La Repubblica and RaiNews at the following links:

https://www.ansa.it/canale_scienza_tecnica/notizie/tecnologie/2020/05/04/cerotti-ultrasottili-per-rigenerare-i-tessuti-2ef019f5-6835-4972-94f4-507e88e4e6ce.html

¹ Vannozzi, L., Gouveia, P., Pingue, P., Canale, C., & Ricotti, L. (2020). Novel ultrathin films based on a blend of PEG-b-PCL and PLLA and doped with ZnO nanoparticles. ACS applied materials & interfaces, 12(19), 21398-21410.

https://www.repubblica.it/scienze/2020/05/04/news/un_microcerotto_per_rigenerare_le_cartilagini-255624503/

<https://www.rainews.it/dl/rainews/media/Ricerca-un-cerotto-ultrasottile-per-rigenerare-le-cartilagini-aed883fe-2e7b-40e6-8507-ccb1f0606f90.html#foto-1>

- 2- Lorenzo Vannozi, ADMAIORA Technical Manager (Figure 10), was interviewed during the TG3 news (RAI – Italian State Broadcaster). The full interview (in Italian) is available on the Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna website at the following link:

<https://www.santannapisa.it/it/multimedia/rai-3-cerotti-ultrasottili-rigenerare-i-tessuti-pubblicati-i-risultati-della-ricerca>

Figure 10: Lorenzo Vannozi, ADMAIORA Technical Manager

4.4 ADMAIORA Project turns 1 year – Promotional video

This video showed the research team of The BioRobotics Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, describing the first year of ADMAIORA Project, with the aim, the progress and the next challenges of the research project funded by European Commission for the innovative paradigm of the osteoarthritis.

The video was properly promoted on the Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna social channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), and the ADMAIORA social channels (Facebook, Twitter):

- The Facebook account of The BioRobotics Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna: <https://www.facebook.com/165421993522527/videos/157541505296450>.
- The Facebook account of ADMAIORA Project (Figure 11): <https://www.facebook.com/403089400253267/videos/792435187921442>

The video reached more than 3000 people.

Figure 11: ADMAIORA Project turns 1 year: video on ADMAIORA Facebook page.

5 Conclusions

This Deliverable describes the key dissemination and communication events organised during the second year of the ADMAIORA project. In particular:

- The Symposium organised by the Project Coordinator, in collaboration with Prof. Sonia Fiorilli, Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy, as Co-Chair, during the 47th ESAO Congress. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 pandemic the event was postponed to September 2021;
- The webinar of Prof. Ricotti during the TechShare event;
- The non-technical Workshop organised in collaboration with IOR, targeting clinicians;
- Two articles on "*Il notiziario del Malato Reumatico*" published by AMRER (an association of patients);
- A TV interview on the RAI – Italian State Broadcaster, which reached ~ 1 million people;
- A press release for a scientific paper published in ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces;
- A promotional video "ADMAIORA turns 1 year".